

MODELING AND ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES *

Tai, Nyan-Hwa (Material Science Center, National Tsing Hua University, Hsinchu, Taiwan, Republic of China)

Chou, Tsu-Wei (Center for Composite Materials, University of Delaware, Newark, DE 19716, U.S.A.)

ABSTRACT

A model for pressure-driven, temperature-gradient chemical vapor infiltration for ceramic matrix composites fabrication has been examined in this paper. The reinforcement in this analysis is in the form of fibrous mats; the deposited matrix is SiC which is obtained from thermal decomposition of methyltrichlorosilane (MTS) gas under excess hydrogen. The matrix deposition on fiber surface is simulated by a quasi-steady-state approach. The temperature distribution, velocity profile, and pressure increment at the vapor inlet have been theoretically predicted. Furthermore, the density distribution of the composite during fabrication can be examined by this model.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites fabricated by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) have gained prominence during the past decade. The relatively low fabrication temperature imparts excellent properties of the ceramic matrix composites.

Several CVI processes have been proposed by researchers. Among these methods, the isothermal CVI^[1,2](ICVI) and forced flow, temperature gradient CVI^[3,4] (FCVI) are most well known. The ICVI process involves the infiltration of vapor species into a fibrous preform, which is situated in an isothermal chamber and matrix grow from the fiber surface as a result of solid product deposition from the chemical reaction of the vapor species. The driving potential for infiltration of the reactants into the fibrous preform is the concentration gradient. The FCVI process consists of the forced flow of vapor reactants in a fibrous preform with temperature gradient and the chemical reaction of the precursors to form the matrix. A number of theoretical studies for both the ICVI^[5-7] and FCVI^[8,9] processes have been reported for the investigation of the influence of the processing parameters on product density and processing period.

Both the ICVI and FCVI processes have their advantages and inherent drawbacks. For example, premature pore closure may occur if the reaction condition is not optimized in the ICVI process and a long processing period is needed. The ICVI process is desirable for fabricating composite parts with complex shapes. On the other hand, the FCVI process is limited to simple mold configuration, but this process drastically reduces the processing period.

The present study considers the pyrolysis of the MTS gas under excess hydrogen in the FCVI process. In this work, a long fiber mat is chosen as the preform. Assuming large aspect ratio of the rectangular preform, a two-dimensional approach is adopted for simplicity. The schematic view of the preform in the deposition chamber with pressure and temperature gradients is shown in Figure 1. The concentration variation of the reactants has been taken into account in this work. Based upon this model, the variations of the

local density, porosity, and permeability of the preform can be determined as the deposition on the fiber surface proceeds.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The deposited matrix is SiC, which is derived from the pyrolysis of methyltrichlorosilane gas. The chemical reaction is expressed as:

Figure 1 Schematic figure of fibrous preform in a reactor with pressure and temperature gradients

The apparent deposition rate of reaction products, R_d (cm/sec), can be expressed as :

$$R_d = k M_{\text{MTS}} \quad (2)$$

where M_{MTS} is the mole fraction of the MTS gas, and k denotes the reaction rate constant which follows the Arrhenius equation

$$k = 2.8 \times 10^{-2} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

Here, R and T denote the gas constant (8.3143 J/(°K mole)) and temperature (°K), respectively. E_a is the activation energy ($E_a = 120$ kJ/mole is adopted in this study).

In the FCVI process, the mixture of reactants is forced to flow through the preform which is assumed to be an isotropic and homogeneous porous medium at the beginning of the fabrication process. The equation of continuity for the flow of reactants can be expressed as

$$\nabla \cdot \rho A_v \vec{V} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where ρ = density of the vapor mixture, A_v = effective area for vapor flow, and V = local average velocity of the vapor mixture.

It is assumed that the flow of the reactants in the porous preform obeys Darcy's law; thus, the momentum balance can be expressed as

$$u = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad v = -\frac{\kappa}{\mu} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \rho g \right) \quad (5)$$

where u and v denote the reactant velocity in the x and y components, respectively. κ = local permeability of the preform, μ = local viscosity of the vapor mixture, p = local pressure, and g = gravity acceleration constant.

The temperature distribution in the fibrous preform is determined from the following equation for energy balance:

$$\rho C_p A_v (\vec{V} \cdot \nabla T) = \nabla \cdot (A_s K \nabla T) \quad (6)$$

where C_p = specific heat of reactants, A_s = effective area for heat convection within the control volume, A_s = effective area for heat conduction within the control volume, and K = conductivity of the composite materials.

The compositions of the vapor species are obtained from the equation of conservation of mass

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_i A_v \vec{V}) = \nabla \cdot (D_{12, \text{eff}} A_v \nabla \rho_i) - r_b A \quad (7)$$

where ρ_i (g/cm^3) and D (cm^2/sec) denote the density and diffusivity of the MTS vapor in hydrogen, r_b = reaction rate of thermal decomposition of MTS, and A = total deposition surface area in a control volume (cm^2).

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the FCVI process, the reactants are forced to flow through the fibrous preform by applying a pressure gradient between the inlet and outlet. In this study, the outlet pressure is maintained at 1.0 atm. If a constant pressure is also maintained in the inlet, the flow rate decrease as a result of permeability decrease. Curve A in Figure 2 demonstrates the flow rate variation during processing. On the other hand, if a constant flow rate is required, increment in the vapor pressure at the inlet is needed. Curve B in Figure 2 depicts the

pressure adjustment at the inlet (due to the scale of the figure, only part of the data is presented). The non-linear increment of the pressure with time at the inlet is due to the variation of the permeability in the preform. Curves A and B in Figure 3 give, respectively, the permeability and relative density variations with time at the center point of the preform.

Figure 4 shows the temperature distribution after 5 hours of matrix deposition. The temperature distribution strongly depends on the arrangement of the heating elements in the reactor; the temperature decreases from the high temperature region around the heating elements to the low temperature regions in the vicinities of the inlet and outlet.

Figure 5 shows the relative density distribution when the infiltration process is completed. A relatively high density region is observed in most part of the preform. High density gradients around the inlet and outlet are also observed; this is due to the relatively low deposition rate in these two regions.

CONCLUSIONS

A quasi-steady-state approach has been proposed to model the FCVI process and investigate the influence of the temperature distribution on the matrix deposition. The permeability and relative density variation have also been calculated. A non-linear pressure increment at the inlet is needed if a constant flow rate is required. According to the analytical predictions, the fabrication period can be reduced if the temperature of the heating elements is increased and the temperature gradient within the preform is reduced. Premature inlet closure may occur if the temperature at the inlet is high.

Figure 2 Pressure and flow rate variations during processing

Figure 3 Variations of permeability and relative density during processing at the center point of the preform

Figure 4 Temperature distribution after 5 hours of matrix deposition

Figure 5 Relative density distribution after 5 hours of matrix deposition

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